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Investigation of linear alkylbenzene synthesis using nanotitania-supported Dawson heteropolyacid as catalyst by statistical design approaches

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Abstract

Alkylation of benzene with 1-decene for production of linear alkylbenzene in the presence of nanotitania (n-TiO₂)-supported Dawson heteropolyacids was studied. Various operating parameters including benzene to 1-decene molar ratio, catalyst weight percent (wt%), catalyst loading (wt%), calcination temperature, reaction time, and temperature influenced the reaction yield. Fractional factorial design was employed to screen these parameters, and significant parameters modeled by a central composite design. Finally, the best conditions were defined by using nonlinear Nelder-Mead optimization to reach maximum reaction yield.

Keywords

Dawson heteropolyacid, Design of experiments, Design, Linear alkylbenzene, Nanotitania, Supported catalyst, Benzene, Catalysts, Calcination temperature, Central composite designs, Fractional factorial designs, Heteropoly acids, Nanotitania, Operating parameters, Statistical design, Catalyst supports